

RESEARCH ARTICLE

An Investigation of Distance Measures for Development of Effective Content Based Tumor Image Retrieval System

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: The MRI has proven to be extremely effective in detecting tumors, with millions of images created each day throughout the world. To find similar images from a vast collection, Content-Based Tumor Image Retrieval (CBTIR) technology has been used to analysis the medical image. In the traditional retrieval methods, retrieving a similar image from the large database is crucial task. To overcome this issue we developed deep learning based retrieval method. **Methods:** This research offers a retrieval approach based on predefined ResNet models for quick and accurate image retrieval. We tested various prominent ResNet models with different distance similarity metrics, and the best option was determined by this work. **Findings:** After the various evaluation of ResNet models with varied distance measures on the CE-MRI data set, ResNet50 model applied with Hamming distance yields 99.33% of retrieval precision. **Novelty:** This work used predefined ResNet models with the combination of Distance similarity metrics to achieve more accurate results on medical image retrieval compared to the other conventional methods.

Keywords: Content Based Image Retrieval; Tumor Retrieval; Hamming Distance; Euclidean Distance; Minkowski

1 Introduction

Medical imaging technology generates a large volume of data in every single day, causing an interruption in the clinical progression. For this reason, scientists have demonstrated concentration in content-based image retrieval systems (CBIR), such as MRI, X-ray, and CT⁽¹⁾. Radiologists may struggle to retrieve MRI images manually from a vast collection of images with similar structures or looks. This will be governed by the radiotherapist's availability and ability to review and retrieve tumor portion images. For large quantities of data manual retrieval procedure is inefficient, tough to replicate, and it take more time. To rectify this issue, automated CBIR could index archive photos with minimal involvement from radiologists. The motivation of this research is retrieving tumor portion images. The CBIR technology retrieves the specific tumor images based on the query image. For the new instance, the radiotherapist retrieved similar or the same images and previous diagnosis details from the repository.

The proposed work is depicted in Figure 2. The purpose of the CBTIR system is to fetch images from the database that is comparable to the query image. At first, features of tumor images in the training database are extracted and stored. The retrieved features are then saved in a repository. Following that, fetch the query image's features from the test dataset. These two extracted features are compared to calculate the similarity measure using different techniques like Euclidean distance (ED), Manhattan distance, Minkowski Distance, and Hamming distance (HD). HD is the best distance-measure technique.

Fig 2. The flowchart of the proposed work

In the proposed investigation, we employ a transfer learning concept with all ResNet model versions and evaluate the results on the CE-MRI dataset⁽¹⁾. We examine all ResNet models, including ResNet50, ResNet50v2, ResNet101, ResNet101v2, ResNet152, and ResNet152v2, using Euclidean (ED) and hamming distance (HD) metrics to determine which model produces the best results for the CBTIR system. This model extracts image features automatically for testing as well as training images. The similarity measure is particularly significant in this procedure since it will be used to get similar images from the repository⁽¹³⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

To test the models, initially, we set a number of images to retrieve as 30. Row 1 of Figure 3 depicts the ResNet50 model's output. In this illustration, Figure 3 (a) stands for the query image, and Figure 3 (b) stands for the retrieved images comparable to the query image. The ResNet50 model retrieved 20 MRI brain tumor images with similar shapes from the 30 images.

The visual representation of the ResNet101 model's output is shown in Figure 3 row 2. In this diagram, Figure 3 (c) denotes the user image, and b indicates the tumor portion images that were retrieved. From the obtained 30 images that are comparable to the query image selected by the user the ResNet101 model retrieved 3 accurate tumor images and 27 MRI brain images with identical shapes.

The visual representation of the ResNet152 model's output is shown in Figure 3 row 4 column 1. The query image is denoted by Figure 3 (g) whereas the retrieved tumor images are represented by Figure 3 (h). The ResNet152 model obtained a large number of precisely matching images that have a comparable shape to the request image. Figure 3 row 4 column 2 and column 3 depicts a graphical representation of the ResNet101V2 and ResNet152V2 respectively. These models retrieved only a few similar images. As a result, we figured out that these models are unsuitable for the tumor retrieval processes.

Fig 3. Visual representation of the proposed ResNet models

Figure 3, row 3 gives the retrieval results of the ResNet50v2. This model finds 40 equivalent images. When compared to the remaining ResNet models, the ResNet50 and ResNet50V2 will produced better outcomes. The percentage of retrieval precision is more important than a quality validation. We calculate the retrieval precision value using the following equation⁽¹⁴⁾. The precision value for each ResNet model listed in Table 1 are calculated for the distance measure ED and HD respectively.

$$precision = \frac{No.of.relevant\ retrieved\ images}{No.of\ retrieved\ images}$$

Table 1. Retrieval Precision value

Models	Precision For HD (%)	Precision For ED (%)
ResNet50	99	90
ResNet101	853	72
ResNet152	62	70
ResNet50V2	89	85
ResNet101V2	54	49
ResNet152 V2	45	40

Table 1 proved that the ResNet50 generates higher precision of above 90% for ED and 99% for HD. Finally, a few existing methods result were compared with our proposed method and given in Table 2.

From Tables 1 and 2, we figured out that ResNet50 performs better than the other ResNet models for the CBTIR system with HD as an index for similarity measure calculation.

Table 2. Comparison of the precision value with existing methods.

Methods	Similarity metrics	% Precision
Garg and Dhiman ⁽¹²⁾	ED	85
Monowar et al. ⁽¹⁵⁾	ED	83
Abdullah ⁽¹⁶⁾	HD	98
Proposed ResNet50	ED	90
Proposed ResNet50	HD	99

4 Conclusion

In this study, we implemented a CBTIR method to retrieve tumor images from a large database. Accessing similar or the same images from the wide database is a crucial process. To overcome this issues researchers produced a variety of CBIR methods using variety of measures. Deep learning methods have an excellent scope in all methodologies due to their rapid retrieval process. Based on the results of this investigation, we developed an automatic CBTIR system utilizing CNN and ResNet50 models with HD metrics. In the future, we provide a rapid method to retrieve exact tumor images with similar grades and diagnostic information.

Declaration

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